

CONTRASTIVE STUDY OF ANTONYMS AND CONVERSIVES IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This thesis examines antonyms and conversives in English and Uzbek through a contrastive analysis of their structural and semantic properties. Focusing on categories like gradable, complementary, relational, and conversions, it identifies both shared principles and unique distinctions, such as Uzbek's use of the passive voice in antonym formation. Findings aim to support English language education by enhancing understanding of antonymic structures.

Keywords: contrastive analysis, antonyms, conversives, semantics.

Introduction. Antonyms and conversives are essential components of lexical semantics, playing a crucial role in understanding opposites and relationships between words in different languages. With English becoming a dominant global language, mastering its nuances, including antonyms, has become vital, particularly in countries like Uzbekistan, where English education is growing. The objective of this study is to provide a contrastive analysis of antonyms and conversives in the English and Uzbek languages, focusing on their structural, functional, and semantic aspects. The study seeks to offer insights into the similarities and differences between the two languages, contributing to the development of more effective teaching strategies for English learners in Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods. This research employs a comparative-typological analysis, using distributive, contrastive, comparative, and historical-comparative methods to examine antonyms and conversives in both languages. The primary materials used for analysis include antonyms in Uzbek and English, with a focus on the works of leading scholars in lexical semantics, such as V.V. Vinogradov, A.I. Smirnitsky, and L.A. Novikov, alongside studies by Uzbek linguists like R. Shukurov and L. Raupova. By reviewing these theoretical perspectives, the study aims to identify key patterns in the use and categorization of antonyms and conversives in both languages.

Results. The study identifies four primary categories of antonyms in both English and Uzbek:

1. **Gradable Antonyms:** Words that lie on a continuous spectrum, such as *hot - cold* in English and *issiq - sovuq* in Uzbek. These antonyms can take intermediate forms.
2. **Complementary Antonyms:** Opposites that do not fall on a continuous spectrum, such as *mortal - immortal* and *odd - even* in English. In Uzbek, examples include *yolg'onchi - haqiqatgo'y*.
3. **Relational Antonyms:** Words that represent opposite roles in a relationship, such as *teacher - student* or *buy - sell* (in English: *to buy - to sell*; in Uzbek: *sotib olish - sotish*).

4. **Antonyms by Conversion:** Unique to both languages, these antonyms present actions or situations from different perspectives. For instance, *to win - to lose* (*yutmoq - yutqizmoq* in Uzbek) are considered conversions.

A key difference noted is that in Uzbek, the passive voice often plays a role in forming antonyms, while in English, the passive voice does not typically serve this function. For example, in Uzbek, *Ishchilar uy qurishyapti - Uy ishchilar tomonidan qurilyapti* (The workers are building the house - The house is being built by the workers) demonstrates a passive conversion, a pattern rarely seen in English.

The study also highlights the use of affixes in forming antonyms in both languages. In Uzbek, the suffix *-emas* is frequently used to negate meaning (e.g., *oson - oson emas*), while in English, prefixes like *non-* and *un-* serve similar functions (e.g., *kind - unkind*).

Discussion. The findings suggest that while antonyms in both languages share fundamental characteristics, cultural and linguistic differences lead to variations in their structure and usage. The passive voice in Uzbek plays a more active role in the creation of antonyms, whereas English relies more on prefixes and syntactic patterns. Additionally, the concept of "antonymic degree" is crucial for understanding the extent of opposition between words. In both languages, antonyms can express varying levels of contrast, ranging from complete opposition to partial opposition, depending on the context.

This study also points out that antonyms are not always strictly defined, and depending on the speaker's perspective, antonyms from one type of opposition may be reinterpreted as another. For example, *gradual antonyms* can sometimes overlap with *relational antonyms*, highlighting the fluid boundaries in linguistic categorization.

Conclusion. The contrastive analysis of antonyms and conversives in English and Uzbek reveals that both languages employ similar semantic and structural principles, but with distinct variations shaped by cultural and linguistic factors. These findings are significant for language educators, particularly in Uzbekistan, where English is increasingly taught as a second language. A deeper understanding of antonymic relationships can help enhance the teaching of English and promote more effective language acquisition strategies. Further research could explore antonyms in other parts of speech, such as nouns and prepositions, to extend the application of these findings across a broader range of linguistic features.

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